

2015

APR-MAY

**Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education Research
Journal (AMIERJ)**

**(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948**

VOL - IV Issues: III

**Chief-Editor:
Ubale Amol Baban**

**UTILITY OF SOMATIC INKBLOT SERIES IN ASSESSING BODY IMAGE
DYSPHORIA IN YOUNG ADULTS**

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Abstract: *The present study was conducted on Utility of Somatic Inkblot Series-II in Assessing Body Dysphoria in Young Adults. A sample of 200 young adults varying by gender (100 Male And 100 Female), individually, following standard procedures (Cassell, 1980), were administered the somatic inkblot series to ascertain projective assessed aspects of body image in adulthood. Descriptive statistic (mean, standard deviation) and t-ratios were computed to compare the two groups' in terms of significance of mean differences which are reported in table. There are significant differences in the PG male students and PG female students with regard to some SIS-II precepts.*

Key words: *body image dysphoria, SIS-II, drive for thinness; eating disorder risk;*

The 20th century has seen the tolerances for weight and body shape narrow dramatically. The 1960s and 1970s witnessed the growth of the women's movement And emphasis began to be placed on a lean and androgynous appearance {Schwartz. 1986; Wooley & Wooley, 1986), With the 1980s came an obsession with exercise (Seid, 1989), and also the introduction of the formal diagnosis of anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa (American psychiatric association 1987) Body image concerns among children and adolescents are becoming increasingly prevalent in developed and developing nations (see Anderson-Fye, 2009, for a review). Two factors are implicated in this: intra cultural factors associated with modernization, such as the improved status of women, and intercultural factors associated with globalization, particularly relating to exposure to the Western media and Western body ideals (Markey, 2004). It is difficult to compare responses across cultures due to differences in the aesthetic salience of body dimensions and body parts. Most notably, the focus on a large and muscular physique for boys

and a small and slender physique for girls is not universal. These ideals might apply in Western cultures (e.g., Australia, the United Kingdom, and the United States; McCabe & Ricciardelli, 2004b; Murnen, Smolak, Mills, & Good, 2003); however, people from both Fiji and Tonga assign a high cultural value to both males and females having a larger body size (Becker, 1995; Mavoia & McCabe, 2008; Williams, Ricciardelli, McCabe, Waqa, & Bavadra, 2006). Asian cultures (especially in China, Korea, and Malaysia) have a preference for slender physiques for both males and females, usually smaller than what is preferred in Western cultures (Jung & Forbes, 2007; Leong, Poh, & Ng, 2004; Pon, Mirnalini, & Mohd Nasir, 2004), whereas Chilean boys and girls have demonstrated a preference for a lean body build (Webb, 2015; McArthur, Holbert, & Pena, 2005; Mellor, McCabe, Ricciardelli, & Merino, 2008). Therefore, whereas body mass index (BMI) is associated positively with body dissatisfaction in Western and Asian cultures (Mellor et al., 2009; Stice, 2002; Yates, Edman, & Aruguete, 2004 Camp, & Stephanie 2015), this relationship is weaker in the Pacific Island countries that favour larger body types (Becker, Burwell, Gilman, Herzog, & Hamburg, 2002; McCabe, Ricciardelli, Waqa, Goundar, & Fotu, 2009). It would certainly appear that the socio-cultural message about body size, as well as the actual size of adolescents' bodies, is associated with levels of body dissatisfaction (Ricciardelli, McCabe, Williams, & Thompson, 2007). Eating related disorder (witcomb et al., 2015

Objective: The present study intends to examine the Utility of Somatic Inkblot Series in Assessing Body Dysphoria in Young Adults.

Method:

Sample: 200 PG students (100 female and 100 male) were selected from Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra ranging in age from 21 to 25 year with the mean age of 23 year. The sample was reconstructed with respect to urban area and middle class family status. It was ensured that they were free from psychiatric symptoms.

Measures: SIS -II is a self-administered test (Cassell 1980, 1990) and consists of inkblots to stimulated somatic precepts. The subjects were required to report what they see in this instructed inkblot. It takes nearly 30 minutes for administration. The reliability and validity of SIS-II have been found to be very high (Pershad and Dubey, 1994 and Cassell, 1988).

Procedure: After establishing the rapport The Somatic Inkblot Series-II was administered individually to each subject following standard procedures (Cassell, 1990) in a distraction free environment. Then the protocols were scored according to manuals and data was analysed to generate the findings.

Statistical analysis: The obtains data was statistically analyzed. Mean Standards Deviation were calculated. t- Ratios were computed to compare the two groups' in terms of significance of mean differences

Results and discussion: Perusal of table reveals that there are significant differences in the PG Male students and PG Female students with regard to some SIS-II precepts. It can be notes from Table that female PG students have scored significantly lower on Human (HR), Sex (SR), Movement (MR), Most Typical (MTR), Typical (TR), Rejection(R), Hostility - Aggression (HAS) scales of SIS-II than male students.

Table 1

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
R	60.81	1.541	60.52	1.438	1.516

1. Total number of responses (R): The number of responses on inkblots is indicative of scored productivity (Beck et.al.1961). According to Cassell (2002) the total number of responses suggests imaginative capacity and functioning intelligence of a subject. Total number of responses is significantly lower among male students as compared to female students. All the males produced less R than females, that's depicts women are more imaginative. Male and female were not found to be significantly different on t values. Male and female were not found to be significantly different on t values.

Table 2

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
HR	23.13	6.373	25.59	6.250	-3.017

2. HUMAN RESPONSE (HR): The human action responses indicate the phenomena of “internalization”, reflecting the ability of an examinee to handle the more deliberate and sophisticated experience in a way that can be controlled emotionally (Rorschach, 1942). The responses indicating human action indicate awareness towards the external world and reflect some conflicts or emotions which do not get obvious expression in the world of reality (Beck, 1952). In the present study we found significant differences in male and female. The number of Human responses suggests males have better interpersonal relationship with human beings. The early workers found a range of 7.87% to 17% H responses in normal population (Beck et. al. 1961; Kumar, 1961; Prabhu, 1967; Asthana, 1971; Dubey, 1989).

Table 3

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
AR	9.27	5.061	8.91	4.306	0.591

3. Animal Responses (A) According to Cassell (2002).A large number of animal responses mean that the respondent is less comfortable with people or is psychologically immature. In

general an excess of animal content indicates intellectual constriction and/or emotional disturbance. The person recognizes chiefly the more mundane stimuli and fails to venture in novelty. In the present study, female produced more responses in comparison to males but they have no significant differences on animal responses.

Table 4

Variable s	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
At	13.87	5.210	6.70	4.062	11.884

4. Anatomical Responses (At): Manic females produced higher anatomical responses in comparison of manic males (Kumar, et al 2006). According to Cassell (2002), internal organ responses pertain to internal parts of living beings and their mutilated forms both of humans and animals. These responses are consistently high in those who have a poor self- image and who are preoccupied with internal body organs. Rav (1951) theorized that restriction and reduction in intellectual drive increases recourse to IO responses. Phillips and Smith (1953) regarded IO responses as reflecting a concern with destructive impulses. High mean score on the scale of anatomical responses in female it may be because of somatic hypersensitivity, somatization, body image dysphoria, appearance anxiety, and figure consciousness. Otherwise there is no significant difference in both male and female.

Table 5

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
Sex	2.60	1.515	5.66	3.88	-8.051

5. Sex Responses (Sex): There were statistically significant differences on Sex responses between male and female in present study. Male students scored significantly high than female

scored. Study shows that men's sex drives are not only stronger than women's, but much more straightforward. Women place more value on emotional connection as a spark of sexual desire. But women also appear to be heavily influenced by social and cultural factors as well.

Table 6

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
M	17.45	6.647	19.64	6.091	-2.663

6. Movement Responses (M) Rorschach (1942) suggested that M responses indicate the phenomena of "internalization". The M responses reflect the ability of an examinee to handle the more deliberate and sophisticated experience in a way that can be controlled emotionally. Beck (1948) reported that M responses indicate awareness towards the external world and reflect some conflicts or emotions which do not get obvious expression in the world of reality. Cocking, Dana & Dana (1969) found that M responses are related with intellect, fantasies and time estimation. Page (1957) also found the relation of M with fantasy activity.

Table 7

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
MT	10.65	2.546	11.88	1.548	-4.504

7. Most Typical Responses (MT): According to Cassell (1993), the most typical responses are suggestive of coherent, logical thinking and ability to keep up with the demands of society. It

may also be interpreted as a measure of ego strength and team concept. The most common responses reflect the ability to participate in communal or popular thinking within a specific culture or the conformity of the individual's thinking to that of the group. There were statistically significant differences on MT responses between male and female students. On the scale of MT male students have scored significantly higher than female students.

Table 8

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
T	25.37	7.096	25.82	6.541	-0.511

8. Typical Responses (T): A response indicating an appropriate shape reflects that the examinee has respect for the reality of the environment (Beck 1945). There were no statistically significant differences on typical responses between both male and female. Both are well understandable in terms of wide experience of young adults through more cognitive, affective and psychosocial maturity. Hence present findings depict high level of reality testing and healthy perceptions.

Table 9

Variables	Female students(N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
AT	3.41	2.232	3.66	2.310	-0.853
Rej	1.21	1.533	1.48	1.402	-1.406
PAS	5.08	2.277	5.08	1.758	6.219
D	6.38	4.994	4.35	2.180	4.088
HAS	7.47	4.243	9.32	4.609	-3.250

9. Atypical Responses (AT): According to Cassell (2002), atypical responses are those of poor quality and with vague percept either in structure or verbalization. The number of shape inappropriate responses is proportionate to the degree of psychological or psychiatric disturbance. There were no statistically significant differences on AT responses between both groups. It is because perceived sensations are not processed and organized by secondary elaboration mechanism which involves ego-functioning. Higher involvement of ego-functioning is linked with higher functioning of secondary elaboration that makes up poor, vague percept a more logical, coherent and meaningful percept. Therefore, a decline of AT is an indication of sound ego functioning.

10. Rejection of Images (Rej): Cassell (1993) stated that rejection of images shows thought blockage and an inability to think properly. Rejection is the result of an inhibition or blocking of thought, more often a shock phenomenon in most cases (Bohm, 1958). There were no statistically significant differences on Rejection of images between both male and female. Both groups are equally having psychosocial and academic maturity Moreover both tend to have more varied dynamic and goal conflicts.

11. Pathological Scale

a) Pathological Anatomy Scale (PAS): Subjects who have personal health concerns, or who are pathologically identified with the health of others, may project responses in which the body is seen as diseased. PAS indicative of excessive personal health concern, pathological identification with decreased anatomy and hypochondriacally tendency. There were statistically significant differences are found between both male and female. Females scored higher than male member. Young adults, particularly females, tend to be more sensitive and conscious of their appearance and body image because of repeated comparison with healthier personal, actresses and models of their identification, body image dysphoria and appearance anxiety. Gross (2005) also found that 39% of males who were overweight perceived themselves as overweight compared with 68% of overweight females with body size dissatisfaction. Fox, (1997) women are much more critical of their appearance than men – much less likely to admire what they see in the mirror. Up to 8 out of 10 women will be dissatisfied with their reflection, and more than half may see a distorted image.

b) Depression (D): There were statistically significant differences are found between both male and female. Females scored higher than male member. For female students, depression can be attributed to stressors such as academic pressure, financial worries, inadequate social adaptation, inadequate sleep, and the stress of the overall transition to college life. Poor eating habits, and not enough exercise make up a recipe for depression among college students. College-aged women experience greater distress, ruminate on a former relationship longer, and have higher rates of sadness, anxiety, and overall negative emotions than do young men.

c) Hostility and Aggression Scale (HAS): There were statistically significant differences are found between both male and female. Males scored higher than female member on SIS-II scale of HAS. Aggressive behaviour comes in two forms. The first is “reactive–impulsive,” which are responses to external threats. The second is “appetitive-aggressive,” which is internally motivated. It is derived from the intrinsic pleasure that is associated with violence, hunting, and combat. Frustration creates a motive for aggression.

Table 13

Variables	Female students (N=100) Mean	Female Students' SD	Male Students (N=100) MEAN	Male Students' SD	T
P	3.10	2.897	2.18	1.314	3.185

d) Paranoia Scale (P). There were statistically significant differences are found between both male and female. Females scored higher than male member on SIS-II scale of P. "paranoia is the new depression" among young women. Often, paranoid thoughts and feelings are related to events and relationships in a person's life, thereby increasing isolation and difficulty with getting help. Some environmental leads frustrations in female

Conclusion: On the basis of our result and in the light to the discussions of a few studies, it can be said that sex differences were found in our sample. Both the groups showed differences in certain factors like emotional construction, abundance of creative impulses dependency, high degree of empathy, difficulty in establishing close personal relationship and anxiety concerning bodily functions. Findings of the present study depicts young female adults to be more

characterized by body image dysphoria, appearance anxiety, sexual anxiety, over health concerned, depressed mood . Sex differences in body shape found in this study. It found that women are more likely than man describes themselves as overweight. Worry about being or becoming fat. Express greater concern with dieting and body weight. Therefore, more likely to feel distressed about their body image and put forth more effort to alter their shape. Men are now adopting the same unrealistic standard, they defining themselves more by looks Women are pressured to be lean and thin, and men are pressured to be lean and muscular. Relationship status can be particularly stressful process, possibly leading to pressure enhance their physical attractiveness and or alter their body shape.

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